

ISic2758

I.Sicily inscription 2758

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

prayer

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Dianae Fons

Place of origin (modern)

Comiso

Provenance

Area of Crucidda

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331214

1. [— — — — — — — — —]
2. [...c.11.... (e.g.) πλοίθουνον κέ]
3. [τὺς] καρπ [ὺς κέ . . c.8. . . τῆς]
4. [χό]ρας κέ ἀμπε[λ]ῶνος Παύλου· ἴδ-
5. [ε] ἐπ' ἀτοῦ τοῦ κοίτου αὐτο[ῦ]. □
6. Ἀβιμηλ. Λασθηλ. Ἀμιαηλ.
7. [.c.5.] Ξαο. Αζαηρ.
8. [— — — — — — —]
9. ²vestigia crucum et signorum magicorum²
- 10.

Edition: PHI332931

1. [— — — — — — — — —]
2. [τὺς] καρπ [ὺς vacat (?)]
3. [χώ]ρας κέ ἀμπελῶνος ²⁶ἀμπελῶνας = ἀμπελῶνος²⁶ Παύλου, ἴδ-
4. [ε] πάτον, τὸν κοίτον αὐτο[ῦ]. □
5. Ἀβιμήλ, Λασθήν, Ἀμιαήλ,

6. [Υ] γ,ί,α , Γαο ²⁶Ιαω(?)²⁶ Ἀζαήε.

7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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